

Experimental and Numerical Investigation of a Bio-Based Nano-Enhanced Phase Change Material Integrated within a Thermal Energy Storage System: Early Results

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Abstract

Global energy demand and the limitations of fossil fuels have accelerated interest in renewable energy and efficient storage technologies. Solar thermal systems paired with latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) offer a promising solution, relying on phase change materials (PCMs) to store and release heat during phase transitions. However, conventional PCMs such as paraffins exhibit low thermal conductivity, which restricts system efficiency. The use of nanoparticles has been studied as an effective approach to enhance heat transfer. This study presents a preliminary evaluation of the performance of a commercial organic fatty acid PCM and its nano-enhanced counterpart incorporating 4 wt.% graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs). Both materials were tested experimentally and numerically within a small lab-scale domestic hot water storage tank. Results show that the nano-PCM accelerates melting and solidification, reducing melting time by 6 min and increasing the discharge temperature by about 1.3 °C compared with pure PCM. CFD simulations showed good agreement with the experimental results. Overall, the incorporation of GNPs markedly improves LHTES performance, enabling more efficient and reliable solar thermal systems.

Keywords

Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage, Nano-Enhanced Phase Change Materials, Graphene Nanoplatelets, Computational Fluid Dynamics

1 Introduction

The increasing global demand for energy, driven by population growth and rising requirements for thermal comfort, is placing significant pressure on conventional energy systems. The built environment is responsible for approximately 35% of greenhouse gas emissions, and 85% of buildings in Europe are older than 25 years. Thermal energy storage (TES) can enable the efficient uptake and utilisation of renewable energy and can be readily integrated into building systems [1].

Among TES technologies, latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) using phase change materials (PCMs) has received considerable attention due to its high energy storage density and near-isothermal behaviour during phase transitions [2]. PCMs represent a compact and mature TES technology with a high technology readiness level (TRL). Despite these advantages, their development faces significant techno-economic challenges at the material, component, and system levels [1]. Key challenges include achieving high thermal conductivity, sufficient thermal and chemical stability under repeated cycling, and maintaining cost-effectiveness and sustainability [3].

The inherently low thermal conductivity of PCMs has led to the development of nano-enhanced phase change materials (NePCMs), achieved by dispersing high-conductivity nanoparticles such as graphene, metal oxides, and other carbon-based materials into the base PCM [3]. This approach improves thermal conductivity and heat transfer performance; however, it may introduce trade-offs, including reduced latent heat capacity, increased viscosity, potential stability issues, and higher material costs.

Among carbon-based nanoparticles, graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) have attracted significant attention due to their exceptionally high thermal conductivity and strong potential to enhance PCM performance, as illustrated in Figure 1 [3],[4]. Previous studies have shown that incorporating 4 wt.% GNPs can increase the thermal conductivity of fatty acid-based PCMs by up to 148.9% compared to the base material [5]. Similarly, investigations on organic PCMs,

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including soya wax, beeswax, polyethylene glycol (PEG), and camphene, have reported conductivity enhancements of up to 22% at a concentration of 0.5 wt.% [6]. However, significant discrepancies exist in reported performance improvements, reflecting the strong influence of nanoparticle characteristics, concentration, and dispersion quality [3], [7].

Figure 1: Comparison of thermal conductivity enhancement of NePCMs vs. Nano additive concentration (wt.%) using carbon-based additive [3]

Beyond material-level investigations, PCMs have been widely explored in domestic hot water storage tanks (DHWTs) [8], [11], [12]. However, studies specifically addressing the integration of GNP-NePCMs at the system level, particularly under experimental conditions, remain comparatively limited. Existing numerical studies indicate that GNP-based NePCMs can enhance heat transfer, improve thermal response, and increase peak water temperatures in storage tanks, although the overall benefit depends on system configuration and cost-performance trade-offs [9]. At the material scale, GNP incorporation significantly improves thermal conductivity and reduces melting time, thereby enabling faster charging and improved heat-exchange characteristics [3], [6].

This study presents a preliminary evaluation of a commercial organic fatty acid PCM and its nano-enhanced counterpart containing 4 wt.% GNPs. Both materials are analysed using a purpose-built small-scale thermal storage tank designed for domestic hot water applications. An integrated experimental and numerical methodology is employed to investigate the charging and discharging processes, analyse the evolution of the liquid fraction, and assess the overall thermal performance.

2 Methodology

This section presents the methodology adopted in this study, including the materials considered and the experimental and numerical approaches employed.

2.1 Materials

The base PCM considered in this study is OM55, a commercially available organic material supplied by PLUSS Technologies, selected due to its suitable melting temperature range for domestic hot water storage applications. The NePCM, consisting of OM55 with 4 wt.% graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs, 6–8 nm), was adopted directly from

the work reported in [10], where the material preparation and characterisation were conducted. Therefore, the present study does not address material synthesis but instead focuses on the experimental and numerical evaluation of thermal performance. The thermophysical properties of OM55 and the OM55–GNP composite used in the simulations, obtained from laboratory characterisation and supporting literature in [10], are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Thermal properties of PCM and NePCM [10]

Properties	OM55	NePCM
Density [solid] [kg/m ³]	935	976
Density [liquid] [kg/m ³]	941	980
Specific heat capacity [solid] [kJ/kg. K]	2.68	2.61
Specific heat capacity [liquid] [kJ/kg. K]	2.76	2.7
Latent heat of fusion [kJ/kg]	188	180
Thermal conductivity [solid] [W/m. K]	0.16	0.53
Thermal conductivity [liquid] [W/m. K]	0.11	0.41
Phase change temperature [°C]	55	54

2.2 Experimental Setup

The experimental investigation was conducted using a heat storage tank manufactured in the lab. A small-scale cylindrical acrylic glass thermal energy storage tank (with aluminium caps) was designed to evaluate the performance of a domestic hot water system. The tank had a total water volume of 2.7 L and contained two copper encapsulations filled with PCM, each with a volume of 0.07 L, giving a total PCM volume of 0.14 L. Copper was selected due to its high thermal conductivity (398 W/m.K), which enhances heat transfer between the PCM and the surrounding water. Heat losses were minimised by insulating the tank with a 20 mm layer of thermal foam. A CAD representation of the tank and the arrangement of the PCM containers is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: 3D model of (a) water storage tank, (b) PCM container (macro-encapsulation)

Figure 2a shows the overall appearance of the heat storage tank, which is fully insulated with thermal foam and Figure 2b is the schematic representation of the experimental setup.

Figure 2: a) Prototype Small-scale TES and b) Schematic Setup

An electrical heater supplies hot water to the thermal storage tank through the inlet pipe. Mass conservation is ensured by maintaining equal volumetric flow rates at the inlet and outlet, thereby keeping the total water volume in the tank constant throughout operation. A flow rate of 0.006 L/s was selected, as it provided the most stable operating conditions. Under these conditions, the domestic water heater delivers water at 75 °C with an accuracy of ± 0.5 °C, which is sufficient to meet the melting requirements of the selected PCM (20K above its melting point).

Temperature measurements were recorded using seven K-type thermocouples (accuracy ± 0.25 °C). Six thermocouples were distributed within the tank to monitor water and PCM temperatures at various levels, while one measured ambient temperature. Thermocouple placement is illustrated in Figure 3. Hot water at 75 ± 0.5 °C was introduced into the tank at a controlled flow rate of 0.006 L/s to initiate PCM melting.

Figure 3: Thermocouple location inside the TES

Three configurations were evaluated under different scenarios: (a) water only (baseline), (b) water with macro-encapsulated PCM, and (c) water with macro-encapsulated NePCM. Each experiment was conducted in two stages, charging and discharging.

2.2.1 Charging Process

The charging process involved circulating hot water through the tank for 60 minutes, during which inlet, outlet, and PCM temperatures were continuously monitored. The initial temperatures of both the water and the PCM in the storage tank were set using the domestic water heater. Heat was transferred from the circulating hot water to the experimental setup until all components reached the desired initial temperature. Temperature stabilisation was continuously monitored using thermocouples positioned within the tank.

Following this, the charging process was initiated by supplying hot water at a constant temperature of 75 °C through the inlet. The water flow rate was maintained at 0.006 L/s, and the charging duration was fixed at one hour. Throughout this period, thermocouples recorded the temperature evolution of both the water and the PCM.

2.2.2 Discharging Process

The discharging process consisted of allowing the tank to cool naturally under ambient conditions. Upon completion of charging, the water supply was shut off, and both the inlet and outlet valves were closed simultaneously to isolate the system.

The thermal storage tank was then allowed to cool naturally under ambient room conditions for 12 hours. During this discharging phase, thermocouples continuously recorded the temperature evolution of both the water and the PCM.

2.3 Numerical Model

The charging process of the heat storage tank was numerically simulated using the CFD software ANSYS Fluent 2023 R1. Two simplified computational models were developed based on the main dimensions and physical characteristics of the storage tank with and without macro-encapsulated PCM. The first model represents a cylindrical heat storage tank with a total capacity of 2.7 L. The inlet and outlet pipes have a diameter of 20 mm and a length of 45 mm. The second model retains the same tank geometry but includes two cylindrical copper containers filled with PCM (macro-encapsulation) integrated within the tank, with an internal volume of 0.07 L.

2.3.1 Boundary Conditions

The initial temperatures of both the water and the PCM were set to 23 °C. The boundary conditions, illustrated in Figure 5(a), included heat losses via natural convection from the external tank walls, with the ambient temperature fixed at 13 °C to match the laboratory environment (not climatized). An external convective heat transfer coefficient of 0.5 W/m²K was applied. The tank walls and PCM containers were modelled as copper, with a thermal conductivity of 398 W/m·K. During the charging phase, the inlet water flow rate was maintained at 0.006 L/s, and the inlet temperature was set to 75 °C.

Figure 5: (a) Model boundary condition set-up and (b) model temperature measurement distribution.

Models (a) and (b) shown in Figure 5 exhibit geometric symmetry; therefore, a symmetry plane was applied as a boundary condition to reduce computational complexity and decrease simulation time.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Charging Process

Figure 6 presents the charging profiles of the three configurations: water-only, water with PCM, and water with NePCMs, with simulations. As anticipated, the water-only case exhibited the fastest rise in average water temperature since no latent heat absorption occurred. In contrast, the two PCM systems exhibited slower heating rates, reflecting energy absorption during melting.

Figure 6: Charging profiles of the configurations.

For pure PCM, melting extended over approximately 28 minutes, during which the outlet water temperature plateaued, consistent with the near-isothermal nature of the phase transition. Incorporating GNPs into the PCM reduced the effective melting duration by about six minutes. This can be attributed to the lower latent heat and enhanced thermal conductivity, which enabled more efficient heat transfer through the copper container walls. This performance could be particularly advantageous for solar domestic hot water applications, where rapid charging during intermittent sunlight is desirable.

3.2 Discharging Process

The tank discharge over a 12-hour cooling period is illustrated in Figure 7. Both PCM models maintained outlet water temperatures above those of the water-only baseline, confirming their ability to prolong heat release. While PCM alone demonstrated effective retention, the NePCM composite performed better overall. After six hours, the outlet temperature of the NePCM system was approximately 1.3 °C higher than that of pure PCM. Although the difference narrowed towards the end of the discharge period, the composite still delivered a measurable advantage.

Figure 7: Discharging profiles of the configurations.

This improvement arises from the higher effective thermal conductivity of the NePCM, which not only enhanced charging rates but also promoted more uniform solidification and steadier heat release during cooling. These findings align with earlier reports in which nanoparticle-enhanced PCMs extended discharge periods by reducing thermal resistance in the medium [13], [14].

3.3 Validation

As shown in Figure 7, the experimental and numerical PCM temperature results during the charging process differ by no more than 8%. Regarding the water temperature variations, Figure 6 shows that the experimental and numerical results agree well, with a difference of up to 2%. The numerical results provide an ideal comparison of temperature changes, reflecting the phase change processes of NePCM and PCM. The NePCM in the measured area begins melting at the 10th minute and finishes at the 19th minute, while the PCM begins melting at the 13th minute and finishes at the 25th minute. However, there are some differences between the numerical and experimental results regarding the phase change process of PCM. The NePCM melting and solidification behaviour in macro-encapsulations will be evaluated in future work to provide insights into internal dynamics that could not be easily measured experimentally.

Figure 7: Comparison of the experimental and numerical results for different PCM temperature variations during the charging process

Figure 8: Comparison of liquid fraction of different PCM

Figure 9: Liquid fraction contours at 15 min: a) Pure PCM and b) NePCM.

Figure 8 compares the liquid fraction of the water tank with macro-encapsulated PCM vs. macro-encapsulated NePCM. It clearly shows that NePCM transitions from solid to liquid faster than PCM. NePCM fully converts to liquid in 22 minutes, while PCM takes 28 minutes. Figure 9 shows the liquid-fraction contours for the PCM and NePCM models at 15 minutes, with a higher liquid fraction for NePCM.

4 Conclusions

This study provides a preliminary assessment of an organic phase change material (PCM) and a graphene nanoplatelet (GNP)-enhanced PCM composite (NePCM) in a small-scale hot water thermal energy storage (TES) system. The results demonstrate that both PCM and NePCM can be successfully integrated into domestic hot water tanks, extending thermal storage duration through latent heat mechanisms and improving overall system performance. Key findings are summarised as follows:

- Integration of PCMs into TES tanks enables effective long-term heat storage and controlled heat release via phase change, improving the ability to meet domestic hot water demand. The spatial arrangement of PCM within the tank also plays a critical role, where optimised configurations enhance heat transfer and storage efficiency.
- The NePCM exhibits improved thermal conductivity compared with pure PCM, leading to faster charging and discharging processes. The addition of 4 wt.% GNPs reduces melting time by approximately 6 minutes and promotes more stable thermal discharge, maintaining outlet water temperatures up to 1.3 °C higher over a 6-hour cooling period. Enhanced conductivity also allows faster solidification and more efficient latent heat release.
- Numerical simulations using a CFD model based on the enthalpy–porosity method show good agreement with experimental data and confirm that system-level optimisation, particularly PCM proportion and configuration, is as important as material enhancement.

Overall, GNP-based NePCMs demonstrate strong potential to improve heat transfer and storage efficiency in latent-heat TES systems. Combining advanced materials with optimised system design represents a promising pathway for enhancing the performance and reliability of solar domestic hot water technologies. Future work should focus on evaluating the long-term stability and durability of nano-enhanced materials to ensure sustained performance over repeated thermal cycles. Investigation of alternative tank orientations is recommended, since the present study considered only a vertical configuration, which may influence nanoparticle distribution and thermal behaviour. Further research should explore optimisation of system geometry, including PCM encapsulation and heat exchanger design, as well as their interaction within the tank. Detailed analysis of charging and discharging rates under varying operating conditions is also needed, particularly for integration with different applications such as heat pumps and solar thermal collectors.

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